

Introduction to Engineering Design

Chapter 2

Engineering Design Teams and Roles

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Learning Objectives to be achieved:

1. To identify the way the team will tackle the SDGs
2. To recognize the best way to build a team
3. To determine the characteristics of good team members
4. To acknowledge the abilities of a good team leader
5. To determine how to maintain an effective team that will contribute to the proposed Engineering Design project to address any of the Sustainable Development Goals.

2.0 Introduction

This second week's topics respond to the second-course objective: "On completion of this subject, the students can participate within and contribute to a multi-discipline engineering design team through the application of team roles and communication".

In the first week's discussion, the students are challenged to participate in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) action in any way possible. An example of how the 2019 Engineering Design class performed an engineering design project as a team.

This year's challenge is given to all students or learners enrolled in this class by taking at least two (2) SDGs. To make it happen, The Greening Engineering Framework (GEF) will be a theme for the Engineering Design Challenge 2022.

Understanding the vulnerability of the country (or any country in the world) will help the Engineering design student of any disciplines (mining engineering, mineral processing engineering and civil engineering, etc) working together as a team with focus on a sustainable development design as they explore the country's resources to meet the demands of development.

2.1 Greening Engineering Framework (GEF) as guiding framework to design objectives that tackle SDGs

The Greening Engineering Framework (GEF) is a framework conceptualized to minimize global climatic changes at the local level and contribute meaningfully towards reducing the impacts of global climate change within their societies. An example is that discarded or waste materials that would otherwise threaten public health can be used innovatively and transformed into a new product that addresses a sustainable environment (Betasolo & Chris Kobal).

Figure 9. Greening Engineering Framework, GEF (Betasolo & Chris Kobal) (Secretary-General)

5 GEF Elements

2.1.1. Unitech (or any organization) Vision & Mission (Education)

Example for Unitech

Unitech Vision: To grow world-class technocrats of the real world by 2024 and beyond

Unitech Mission: To grow world class technocrats through high quality experiential teaching, research and ardent application of science, technology and innovations.

Align your sustainable engineering design with your organization's vision and mission by identifying the priorities of your organization and its strategy to get there – the Vision. The mission tells the specifics to get there. There may be many in its mission statement; try to limit your team's priority. Unitech's mission mentions experiential research and the ardent application of science, technology, and innovations. So, the student's interest in creating an engineering design should consist of innovative technologies that have an application of science or technology through research and scientific application.

2.1.2. Innovativeness (Design Intention)

The design conceptualization should look at how SDG's entry points for transformation are in Figure 10. Four (4) Levers are Governance, Finance, Economy, Individual and Collective Action and Science and Technology. Those levers should match the entry points such as Human well-being and capabilities, Sustainable and just economies, Sustainable food systems and healthy nutrition, Urban and peri-urban development, and Global environmental commons.

Figure 10. Entry Points for Transformations of SDGs (Secretary-General)

2.1.3. Resilience (Construction Practices)

In Figure 11, SDGs target trends can support which areas need more support that the student engineering design project can address. For example, primary education has reached closer to the goal, but literacy among youth and adults ranges between 5-10%. To increase this trend, the student engineering design project should support literacy among youth or adults. An innovative way to learn remotely for that adults that don't have access can support the goal of "education for all".

Table 1-1
Projected distance from reaching selected targets by 2030 (at current trends)

GOAL	WITHIN 5%	5-10%	>10%	NEGATIVE LONG-TERM TREND
Goal 1		1.1. Eradicating extreme poverty	1.3. Social protection for all	
Goal 2		2.1. Ending hunger (undernourishment)	2.2. Ending malnutrition (stunting) 2.3. Maintaining genetic diversity 2.a. Investment in agriculture*	2.2. Ending malnutrition (overweight)
Goal 3	3.2. Under-5 mortality 3.2. Neonatal mortality		3.1. Maternal mortality 3.4. Premature deaths from non-communicable diseases	
Goal 4	4.1. Enrolment in primary education	4.6. Literacy among youth and adults	4.2. Early childhood development 4.1. Enrolment in secondary education 4.3. Enrolment in tertiary education	
Goal 5			5.5. Women political participation	
Goal 6		6.2. Access to safe sanitation (open defecation practices)	6.1. Access to safely managed drinking water 6.2. Access to safely managed sanitation services	
Goal 7		7.1. Access to electricity	7.2. Share of renewable energy* 7.3. Energy intensity	
Goal 8			8.7. Use of child labour	
Goal 9		9.5. Enhancing scientific research (R&D expenditure)	9.5. Enhancing scientific research (number of researchers)	
Goal 10			10.c. Remittance costs	Inequality in income*
Goal 11			11.1. Urban population living in slums*	
Goal 12				12.2. Absolute material footprint, and DMG*
Goal 13				Global GHG emissions relative to Paris targets*
Goal 14				14.1. Continued deterioration of coastal waters* 14.4. Overfishing*
Goal 15				15.5. Biodiversity loss* 15.7. Wildlife poaching and trafficking*
Goal 16			16.9. Universal birth registration **	

Figure 11. SDG's Target Trends (Secretary-General)

2.1.4. Sustainability (Retrofitting Practices)

Figure 12, Interaction Among Sustainable Development Goals, shows what problems are pressing on and how the engineering design team can address the problem. For example, the SDG 1 interactions with each other required trade-offs to address the issue.

2.1.5. Entrepreneurial (3Rs (Recycling, Reuse, Recover))

The student engineering design project the team will create should have a commercial value to eliminate poverty and address the "no poverty" issue. Since a budget for students is not provided, they can resort to using available resources that they can recycle, reuse or recover.

Interactions among Sustainable Development Goals

Figure 12. Interaction Among Sustainable Development Goals (Secretary-General)

A. Building & Maintaining an Effective Team

2.2 What are Engineering Design Teams?

- Engineering teams - means of dividing up the workload, who will do. (Wright, 2002)
- specific design tasks - trained engineers (Wright, 2002)
- contribute specialized knowledge and provide organizational competence to solve a problem where the knowledge of any engineer would be inadequate to solve it. (Wright, 2002)
- Members from each of the specialties could be assigned to a task force or a design team for the duration of the design process while reporting to a functional manager in their respective specialty and the project engineer. (Wright, 2002)
- Design teams are often temporary and appointed for a specific purpose, then dissolved when the work is completed. (Wright, 2002)
- A team is define as a small group of people with a complementary skills committed to a common purpose, with performance goals and approach that hold themselves accountable (Developing and Sustaining High-Performance Work Teams, n.d.)

2.2.1 6 Success Factors that Define a Team (Library, n.d.)

- ✓ *A small number of people:* There are fewer than 12 members (sometimes much fewer)
- ✓ *Complementary skills:* The team identifies and uses each member's different perspectives, knowledge, skills and strengths.
- ✓ *Performance goals:* The team has clearly defined objectives for which members are individually and collectively accountable.
- ✓ *Common approach:* There is a shared purpose, with a clear understanding of the team's mission and vision.
- ✓ *Mutually accountable:* The results come from a collective effort rather than the sum of individual efforts. People are responsible not only for their actions but those of others.
- ✓ *Leadership:* The team rotates leadership instead of having a strong solo leader.

2.2.2 Benefits of Working in Teams

Overview:

- ✚ Accomplish more in:
 - ❖ Quantity
 - ❖ Complexity
- ✚ Generate more solutions/brainstorming ideas.
- ✚ Gain exposure to various points of view.
- ✚ Develop/use “critical thinking” and “evaluation” skills.
- ✚ Improve conflict resolution skills
- ✚ Improve communication skills

Detailed:

- ✓ Accomplish projects an individual cannot do – Most engineering projects are too large or too complex for one individual to complete alone. Imagine trying to build a project, the Golden Gate Bridge all by yourself!
- ✓ Brainstorm More Solution Options - Different type of people are looking at the same problem will find different solutions.
- ✓ Detect Flaws in Solutions - A team looking at different proposed solutions may find pitfalls that an individual might miss.
- ✓ Build Community - Members of an effective teams can form personal bonds, which are suitable for individual and workplace morale. In the university setting, students on teams often form bonds beyond the classroom.
- ✓ Exposure to different points of view - You learn different ways of approaching a problem when you are exposed to methods and ideas that other people have.

- ✓ Critical Thinking and Evaluation Skills – You must use these skills to evaluate team project goals' complex issues and formulate appropriate solutions and plans.

- ✓ Conflict Resolution Skills - Yes, teams have conflicts, but you can develop the skills that facilitate solutions that reduce conflicts so that the team remains functional.

- ✓ Students may do more academic work - Some students may accomplish more to move in the same pace with the rest of the team.

- ✓ Communication Skills - A team relies on communication among members.
 - ✓
 - Actively and effectively listen to their team members to understand their ideas and concerns.
 - Effectively articulate their ideas or their concerns to others.
 - Provide genuinely constructive feedback to team members

2.2.3 Who Should be in Your Team?

2.2.3.1 Person with a character of willingness

Willingness is a function of: (Lucas G)

1. Confidence – the person’s feeling that "I can do it."
2. Commitment – the person’s feeling that "I will do it."
3. Motivation – the person’s feeling of,
“I want to do it.”

2.2.3.2 A person who is trustworthy

“To build trusting relationships, we need to communicate with the intent to learn from others, not control them.

Trust is the glue that makes effective collaboration and teamwork possible.

People become competitive or defensive without trust, and communication is distorted and unreliable." (Lucas G)

Where trust is lacking, would you: (Lucas G)

- ✓ Reveal your weaknesses?
- ✓ Feel comfortable about collaborating?
- ✓ Acknowledge a “true” desire to improve?
- ✓ Be able to be critical of the performance of the organization?

2.2.4 Building a TEAM (Lucas G)

Step One: Identification (Multi-disciplinary, 2-3 members)

Step Two: Moving from a list of names to a TEAM

- ✓ Get to know each other (Formally and Informally, team introduction)
- ✓ Share experiences
- ✓ Pedagogy
- ✓ Motivations
- ✓ Expectations
- ✓ Identify strengths and assets

Step Three: Set Ground Rules

Some ground rules:

- ✓ Attendance
- ✓ Promptness
- ✓ Meeting place & time
- ✓ Participation
- ✓ Basic conversational courtesies
- ✓ Assignments

Step Six: **Lead by Example**

A Team Leader can't do it alone...you must involve all team members to reach SUCCESS!!!

Step Four: **Develop a Team Goal /Vision**

How will you get there . . . Create a map!

Some things to consider when developing team goals:

- ✓ Identify **realistic** and **defined** goals
- ✓ What problems to solve? SDG's achievement?
- ✓ What project will solve the problem?
- ✓ Who is responsible for the tasks, and sub-tasks?
- ✓ Who will help you achieve it?

- ✓ How will you **reach** these goals – Prototype
- ✓ How will you **communicate** these goals

Team Goals/Vision

- Define a common goal for the project.
- List tasks to be completed.
- Assign responsibility for all tasks.
- Develop a timeline.
- Develop and post a checklist.
- Maintain a central archive for all communications.
(Drawings, Photos, Report, Presentation)
- Communicate all team meetings.
- Send reminders when deadlines approach.
- Send confirmation when tasks are completed.

Step Five: **Defining Roles and Responsibilities**

- ✓ ***An effective team leader knows how to utilize the strengths of each team member.***
- ✓ Defining team roles and responsibilities creates a sense of purpose and direction for each team member.

Team roles – shared responsibilities.

- Assign a Group Leader
 - (Project manager, Project Team Leader, Facilitator, etc.)
- Distribute the work among member
 - Equivalency-Fairness-Balance
 - Ability-Training-Experience
 - Time and Effort
- Communicate - FREQUENTLY
- Do what you promise to do . . . Be accountable
 - On-time
 - Your best quality work

2.3 Characteristics of effective teams

- ✓ Discussions that involve all members
- ✓ Active listening demonstrated by all.
- ✓ Free expression of feelings and ideas is encouraged
- ✓ **A cooperative, friendly, supportive climate**
- ✓ Everyone understands and is committed to the achievement of the goals.

2.3.1 Abilities of a Good Team Leader

What Makes a Good Team Leader?

- ✓ Listening Skills
- ✓ Flexibility
- ✓ Knowledge: to Get Out of the Way
- ✓ Resourceful: Knows Where and When to Get Help
- ✓ Collaboration Skills
- ✓ Motivator for Adults
- ✓ Organized
- ✓ Leads by Example
- ✓ Firm but Fair
- ✓ Consistent
- ✓ Strong Communication Skills
- ✓ Recognizes and Celebrates the Skills of Others

2.4 How to Maintain a Successful Team?

The success of an engineering design team lies on the team skills, as shown in the Figure 13.

Figure 13. Team skills

- Listen: Listen to other people's ideas. When people are allowed to express their ideas freely, these initial ideas will produce other ideas.
- Question: Ask questions, interact, and discuss the team's objectives.
- Persuade: Individuals are encouraged to exchange, defend, and ultimately rethink their ideas.
- Respect: Treat others with respect and support their ideas.
- Help: Help one's coworkers, which is the general theme of teamwork.
- Share: Share with the team to create an environment of teamwork.
- Participate: All members of the team are encouraged to participate in the team.

B. Engineering Design Team Roles

To succeed in their work, the engineering design team requires guided team roles. According to Usability (Project Team Roles and Responsibilities) is define as creating an interdisciplinary

team that have the right mix of skills that are vital to the smooth and successful performance of any project and the team members have multiple roles or there may be a sub-team that are focused on a particular area. The resource allocation shall depends on the level of expertise of team members the project's scope, and the available budget.

Design Engineer

- ▶ A **design engineer** is defined as an engineer that are focused on the engineering design process in various engineering disciplines (including mining, civil, electrical, mechanical, etc.).
- ▶ Design engineers work on products and systems that adapt and use techniques that are complex, scientific and mathematical. Its skills have emphasis on utilizing engineering physics, other applied sciences for development of solutions for society.
- ▶ The design engineer works usually with a team of different engineering disciplines and other types of designers for the development of conceptual and detailed designs that ensure a product function, performance of product, and its purpose.
- ▶ The design engineer works with marketers or businesses to develop the product concept and specifications that meet the customer requirements and may direct the design effort. A distinction is made in many engineering areas between the "design engineer" and roles of other engineer (e.g. planning engineer, project engineer, test engineer).
- ▶ Analysis tends to play a more significant role for the latter areas, and synthesis is more paramount for the former; nevertheless, all such positions are part of the *overall engineering design process*.

Engineering Design Team

- Chicago Engineering Design Team (EDT) is an interdisciplinary engineering and robotics organization composed of students from the University of Illinois at Chicago (UIC), founded in 2000 by a small group of students that wanted to use the knowledge attained in the classroom in the field of theoretical and applied robotics. EDT is divided into three major teams, electrical, software, and mechanical, that aim to bring robotic engineering to the next level. The organization participates in robotics competitions, organizes various engineering events at UIC, and promotes Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) to the community through outreach events. (Chicago Engineering Design Team)
- The University of British Columbia Design Team (The University of British Columbia Engineering Teams)
- The Papua New Guinea University of Technology Engineering Design Team (PNGUoT-EDT) is a voluntary interdisciplinary engineering membership made up of students and staff that are interested to participate in innovative engineering works through application of learned theories to practice organized by the lecturer of the class, EN 124, Introduction to Engineering Design, Dr Betasolo in 2022, who is also the chair for the Innovation Sub-Committee of the Postgraduate, Research & Innovation Committee.

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